

DEVELOPMENT OF A DUAL STRAIN GAGE BALANCE
SYSTEM FOR MEASURING LIGHT LOADS

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ABSTRACT

A unique strain gage balance force measurement system was designed to meet light load requirements for an airfoil model tested in NASA Langley's Low Turbulence Pressure Tunnel (LTPT). This system was developed to obtain direct force data needed to verify calculated pressure to force correlations used in previous aerodynamic tests [1]. The three-component force measurement system was designed so that the strain gage balances would simultaneously support and measure the following loads:

- Weight of the airfoil (approximately 3.0 lb_f)
- 8.0 lb_f of lift
- 0.5 lb_f of drag
- 16.0 in. lb_f of pitching moment

In addition to these design loads, the system was required to withstand 100 percent overload on all three components. The system is comprised of an airfoil, two strain gaged balances, a thermal flexure and a mounting plate. The sides of the metric airfoil were supported by the two strain gage balances. These balances were connected to the wind tunnel walls via the non-metric panels, a thermal flexure and the mounting plate. The system was designed to allow for the thermal expansion and contraction of the model since expansion or contraction could cause large interactions on the measuring elements of the strain gage balances.

Installation of the system in the Low Turbulence Pressure Tunnel presented another challenge. Clearances between the metric model and the non-metric panels were on the order of 0.010 inch. For the strain gage balances to remain within the previously stated design loads, the measuring beams could not deflect more than 0.001 inch. Therefore, it was imperative that the balances be precisely aligned before installing the center airfoil. Devices such as alignment bars, an electronic inclinometer, and adjustable mounting plates were used to perform the delicate tunnel installation.

Following the system setup, check loads were applied to the metric airfoil and previous laboratory calibration data was repeated in the wind tunnel. Aerodynamic direct force measurement tests have been performed and indicate that the system is meeting its design objectives and verifying data from previous aerodynamic tests.

INTRODUCTION

Design of a force measurement system for NASA Langley's Eppler-387 Drag Model was challenging in that the system was required to simultaneously measure very small axial forces and relatively large normal forces and pitching moments. The force measurement system was designed to measure the following anticipated test loads:

- 8.0 lb_f of normal force
- 0.5 lb_f of axial force
- 16.0 in. lb_f of pitching moment

In addition to measuring these test loads, the system was required to handle initial model loads and a 100 percent overload on all components.

The force measurement system was also constrained by model configuration, which consisted of a metric airfoil with nonmetric panels on each end. The system was required to maintain a 0.010 inch maximum clearance between the metric and nonmetric airfoil. The balances were limited to a physical size of 2.0 inches by 3.7 inches by 0.3 inches.

BALANCE SYSTEM DESIGN

Due to the model configuration constraints, a dual strain gage balance system was conceived. It is shown in figure 1. Two identical three-component strain gage balances were used to support the metric airfoil. Each balance was designed to react half of the aerodynamic loads applied to the center airfoil. Photographs of the strain gage balances are shown in figures 2 and 3. The balances were attached to the model by #2-56 UNF screws

and four dowel pins. An assembly of the Eppler-387 drag model and balance system installed at Langley's Low Turbulence Pressure Tunnel (LTPT) is shown in figure 4. The model and dual balance system spanned the tunnel test section. They were mounted to the large turntable drums on the tunnel side walls.

Due to the large ratio of normal force to axial force (16:1), the balances were designed to have two measuring sections. The measuring section containing a pair of rectangular beams was strain gaged to measure both the normal force and the pitching moment (figures 2 and 3). The measuring section containing a pair of center reinforced beams (figure 2) was strain gaged to measure the axial force. The balances' axial measuring sections were designed with center reinforced beams for stiffening while minimally affecting the axial force output. The strain gages on the measuring beams were wired in a wheatstone bridge arrangement [2]. This arrangement electrically cancels the strains due to forces and moments other than those being measured.

The balances were gaged with NK-06-S022H-50 strain gages which have a nominal resistance of 5000 ohms. This higher resistance was preferable to the 350 ohm resistance typical of conventional transducer gages because it had the capability of allowing higher input voltages while drawing small amounts of current. Higher input voltages yield larger outputs. As a result, the measuring beams were strained to low values while still producing acceptable output voltages. Using the 5000 ohm gages along with the lower strain values allowed the measuring beams to be larger in size. As a result the balances are less fragile and can resist larger overloads. Also, strain gage heat buildup occurring in the 5000 ohm gages will be less than the buildup in the 350 ohm gages for similar input voltages. Because the balances measuring beams have a small mass to act as a heat sink [3], temperature effects of strain gage heating were a concern.

The balances were fabricated using 17-4 ph steel which has high strength and good spring characteristics. However, with the full design loads and all combined overloads present, the balance system had a safety factor of 1.8. While this margin of safety is not large, it was considered adequate since the balances were not likely to have all full design loads applied simultaneously.

INDIVIDUAL BALANCE CHECK CALIBRATION

Before fully calibrating the LTPT model and balance system, the left and right-hand balances were individually check calibrated. A calibration stump and fixture were designed and fabricated to perform this check calibration. The calibration hardware is shown in figure 5. The calibration hardware design allowed direct force application over each

measuring element's electrical moment center. This ability to apply pure forces, 4.0 pounds of normal force and 0.25 pounds of axial force, enabled the generation of the normal and axial force sensitivities. The pitching moment sensitivity was generated by transferring 4.0 pounds of normal force 2.0 inches from the normal force cage section's electrical moment center. The application of these forces indicated that both the left and right-hand balances yielded outputs which corresponded to the expected design values.

LABORATORY MODEL AND BALANCE SYSTEM CALIBRATION

The complete model and balance system was set up on a surface plate following the individual balance check calibration. An extremely precise setup was required in order to maintain metric airfoil to nonmetric panel clearances of 0.010 inch while holding the balances' initial electrical offset values to a minimum. The model was first set up using the dummy balances for alignment. This allowed system placement within a few thousandths of an inch of the required alignment. The end plates were clamped in position to the surface plate as a last step in initial system alignment.

The effort to complete a precise setup began upon completion of the initial system alignment. This precise setup was required for live balance installation so that misalignment could be avoided. Excessive system misalignment would have caused a beam deflection in excess of 0.001 inch, thus overloading the balance.

Precise alignment began with the disassembly and weighing of the metric airfoil so that the amount of balance preload could be determined. The metric airfoil weighed approximately three pounds. Each dummy balance was then loaded with counterweights equal to half of the airfoil weight. This allowed the two nonmetric panels to be precisely aligned by producing panel deflections similar to those present when the metric airfoil was in position. Using a dial indicator to reference similar points, the balance attachment flanges were then aligned by a trial and error method of shimming the nonmetric panels into position.

The dummy balances were then removed and the metric airfoil and live balances installed. Both balances were fitted with lockouts and connected to a power source and readout. This enabled outputs of the balances to be continuously monitored during installation. With the live balances attached to each end, the metric airfoil was raised into place. The alignment dowels were then fitted into their mating holes, the balances secured with screws, and the lockouts carefully removed. The installation and alignment procedure produced an electrical offset of less than

0.700mV with an input of 10.0 volts, which was well within the preload tolerance of the balances.

Initial loading began upon the completion of the system setup. It was noted, during this initial loading, that the calibration data was not very repeatable. A large portion of the errors appeared to be due to temperature effects. With temperature swings of approximately 4 °F, errors encountered were ±7% of the full scale axial force component. Originally the model design featured a set of linear bearings to allow adjustment of model length. As temperature changed, the airfoil expanded or contracted. The linear bearings would not allow the system to readjust until the expansion or contraction could overcome the bearing's friction force. As a result, zero shifts and unpredictable balance preloads were constantly present during the initial calibration attempt.

THERMAL FLEXURE

A thermal flexure, shown in figure 6, was designed and fabricated to reduce this temperature-related calibration error. The flexure was used in place of the linear ball bearings and the left-hand mounting plate. Flexure design considerations included:

- Outline dimensions similar to the existing left-hand mounting plate.
- Soft spring constant in the direction of thermal loads.
- Compression and expansion of ±0.020 inch in the direction of thermal loads.
- Support of model weight, normal force loads, and pitching moment without excessive deflection.

The thermal flexure design met all of these requirements. The flex beams were sized to keep the flexure's outline identical to that of the left-hand mounting plate. The flexure's spring constant is 577 pounds per inch in the direction of expansion or contraction. Therefore, a force of 11.5 lbf applied by thermal expansion or contraction was required to deflect the flexure 0.020 inch. A 0.020 inch deflection results in the flexure having a stress safety factor of 4.6. Model weight, normal force, and pitching moment can combine under certain conditions to apply a load to the flex beams in the normal force plane. Individual flex beams were oriented so that loads were carried in compression or tension with little or no bending moment. This orientation allowed the flex beams to be very stiff to loads in the normal force plane. Leveling brackets and jacking screws were also included in the flexure design because this allowed more flexibility in model system alignment during the wind tunnel installation.

The flexure was then fabricated and installed in a lab setup of the model and

balance system. Use of the flexure made the system setup slightly more difficult. The in-line flexure caused more deflection than that present when the linear bearings were in line. An iterative process of alignment adjustments using jacking screws and shims was required to level the model in two planes while maintaining the 0.010 inch gap between the metric airfoil and the nonmetric panels. The iterative process was completed, the model aligned, and the lab calibration was performed. The thermal flexure corrected the temperature-related calibration difficulty and the zero shifts caused by temperature were practically eliminated.

CONTINUATION OF THE SYSTEM CALIBRATION

Calibration loads were applied to the metric airfoil via a leveling and loading fixture, upon resolution of the thermal expansion and contraction problem. This fixture fit the contour of the airfoil. Eight pounds of normal force was applied over the airfoil's center of pressure, and sixteen-inch pounds of pitching moment was generated by transferring the full normal force two inches forward or aft of the center of pressure. A half-pound axial force was applied as a cable load through a small bell crank assembly. The axial cable was as light as possible to reduce cable sag, which could affect the direction of the applied force vector. Following the sensitivity loadings, cross loads were applied. Data from the left and right-hand balances were combined and system sensitivities were established. First and second order interaction terms were calculated [4]. Finally, to check the system accuracy, a multicomponent loading was performed and the data was reduced using the generated sensitivities and interactions. The worst case system accuracies were determined to be as follows:

Normal Force: ±1.0% of full scale design load

Axial Force: ±3.0% of full scale design load

Pitching
Moment: ±0.5% of full scale design load

The ±3.0% axial force error occurred when two or more components were simultaneously loaded to full design loads. This error was reduced when the applied aerodynamic loads were less than the design loads, which was the case during most of the aerodynamic testing. The axial force error was ±1.0 percent of full scale over the majority of the aerodynamic test range. The accuracy of the dual balance system was very good considering the light load requirements, the large initial preload, and the alignment difficulties.

WIND TUNNEL INSTALLATION

The final step prior to aerodynamic testing was the installation of the model in the LTPT. A procedure similar to the laboratory setup was used. The thermal flexure and nonmetric panels were mounted to the LTPT wall turntables (figure 7). An electronic inclinometer, dial gage indicators, and an alignment bar that spanned the tunnel were used to align the two nonmetric panels. The dummy balances were installed and half of the metric airfoil weight applied to each side. The left-hand balance mounting tab on the thermal flexure's side was initially set level in all planes. This was done because the thermal flexure's spring constant is much softer than that of the solid mounting plate. Therefore, the thermal flexure was expected to deflect under load much more than the solid mounting plate on the right-hand side of the tunnel. The right-hand balance's mounting tab was then shimmed into alignment with the mounting tab on the thermal flexure's side. Following alignment of the mounting tabs, the dummy balances and counterweights were removed. The live balances were attached to the metric airfoil and the leads were guided through holes in the turntables. The metric airfoil and balances were raised into place and connected to the nonmetric panels (figure 8). Tunnel checkloads were applied and the laboratory calibration was repeated. Results were similar to those obtained during the laboratory calibration, thus enabling aerodynamic testing to begin.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

In conclusion, the system setup was tedious and time consuming. However, the balances and the thermal flexure performed very well. System accuracies were calculated to be approximately ± 1.0 percent, on all components, over most of the test envelope. Aerodynamic tests have been completed and the data reduced. Data analysis indicates close agreement with forces and moments that were theoretically predicted and derived from previous aerodynamic pressure tests [5]. Therefore, it was possible to design a dual balance force measurement system that could accurately measure a very small axial force given the previously discussed design constraints.

REFERENCES

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- [4] Hansen, R. H.: "Evaluation and Calibration of Wire-Strain-Gage Wind Tunnel Balances Under Load," Wind Tunnel and Model Test Panel of Advisory Group for Aeronautical Research and Development, Rome, Italy, 1956.
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Full scale design loads

Normal force: 8.0 lbs

Axial force: 0.5 lbs

Pitching moment: 16.0 in.lb

Figure 1. Dual strain gage balance system assembly

**Figure 2. Strain gage balances
LTPT-L & R (Top view)**

**Figure 3. Strain gage balances
LTPT-L & R (Side view)**

Figure 4. Eppler 387 drag model and balance system installed in the low turbulence pressure tunnel

Figure 5. Individual balance calibration hardware

Figure 6. Thermal flexure assembly

Figure 7. Wind tunnel installation of the Eppler 387 model & balance system

Figure 8. Eppler 387 model and balance system